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Leaf-associated methanotrophs drive species-specific methane uptake in temperate trees

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Abstract

Tree foliage is increasingly recognized as an important component of terrestrial methane (CH₄) exchange, yet mechanisms driving variation in foliar CH₄ exchange remain unresolved. We quantified in situ foliar CH₄ fluxes and associated microbial communities at a temperate forest restoration site in Downsview Park, Toronto, Canada, focusing on two species representing extremes of CH₄ uptake: *Tilia americana* and *Prunus virginiana*. Using dynamic leaf chambers coupled with laser-based spectroscopy, we show that foliage of both species acted as a net CH₄ sink, but uptake differed by more than an order of magnitude: mean foliar CH₄ uptake was $-2.4 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in *T. americana* vs. $-0.04 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in *P. virginiana*. Amplicon sequencing of 16S rRNA and particulate methane monooxygenase (pmoA) genes revealed abundant Type I methanotrophs (*Methylococcales*) in *T. americana*, whereas *P. virginiana* hosted sparse methanotroph communities dominated by facultative methylotrophs and low pmoA abundance. These results demonstrate that species-specific foliar CH₄ uptake is closely linked to leaf-associated, most likely endophytic methanotrophic communities, highlighting foliage as a biologically mediated CH₄ sink in temperate trees at a restoration site.